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Interest In Learning Foreign Languages Among Youth In Uzbekistan: Causes And Consequences

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Abstract: This article examines the reasons for the growing interest in learning foreign languages among young people in Uzbekistan, the social, cultural and economic impact of this process, and its future role. It analyzes how language learning has become a factor of personal and professional success today, allows for global communication, and broadens the worldview of young people. It also examines the role of modern technologies in the educational process and the reforms being carried out in the field of learning a foreign language.

Keywords: foreign languages, learning motivation, globalization, modern education, language policy, youth, Uzbekistan, communication, future professions

Introduction.

In the current era of globalization, knowledge of foreign languages is considered not only a criterion for individual development, but also one of the important indicators of the country's development. In recent years, interest in foreign languages, especially English, Russian, Korean, Turkish and other languages, has increased significantly in Uzbekistan. This situation reflects the desire of the younger generation to science, modern technologies, and the acquisition of foreign experience. Today, knowledge of a language creates not only the opportunity to study or work abroad, but also personal development, participation in intercultural dialogue, and the opportunity to become a competitive professional.

The interest in learning foreign languages among the youth of Uzbekistan is associated with several factors. First of all, the state policy on learning foreign languages in the country, in particular, the strong foundation of presidential resolutions and ministerial programs, has put this process on a systematic path. The quality and volume of foreign language teaching is being increased from preschool to university. This strengthens the need and motivation of young people to learn languages.

Also, through modern technologies, online courses, mobile applications, and interactive platforms, students are independently improving their level of knowledge. Many language centers, branches of foreign universities, and online learning platforms operating in Uzbekistan have expanded language learning opportunities. Among young people, knowledge of a foreign language is seen as a tool for participating in foreign grants, scholarships, and internship programs. Young people who know a language also have an advantage in finding a job,

especially in the private sector and international companies.

Social networks, the media, and popular bloggers are also having a significant impact on the increase in interest in learning foreign languages among young people. People who know languages such as English, Korean, Japanese, and German are motivating young people by demonstrating their knowledge and experience to a wide audience online. The number of young people who are independently learning foreign languages through platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, Telegram, and Instagram is increasing. This, in turn, increases the importance of informal forms of education, along with traditional education.

In addition, international olympiads, competitions and academic programs have also made language knowledge a necessity. Language knowledge is required to participate in international scholarship programs such as the El-yurt Umidi Foundation, Chevening, Fulbright, DAAD, Erasmus+. Such programs encourage young people not only to learn a language, but also to test their potential on a global scale.

Uzbek youth are using different approaches in the process of language learning. Some approach it in a traditional way - based on textbooks and grammar, while others prefer a communicative approach, that is, mastering the language through practical communication. In particular, initiatives such as the activities of language clubs and speaking clubs, and the arrival of foreign volunteers to teach in our country are yielding effective results.

Studies show that learning a foreign language not only brings academic or professional benefits, but also improves the cognitive function of the brain, increases attention, memory, and multitasking (the ability to do several things at once). That is why parents are trying to send their children to foreign language courses from an early age, which makes language learning part of the national family values. In today's globalization, language is seen not only as a means of communication, but also as a means of transmitting, acquiring, and sharing knowledge, technologies, cultures, and ideas. In particular, English is recognized as the main means of communication in international business, the Internet, science, and diplomacy. Therefore, young people are accepting language learning as a means of finding their place in the modern world and fully realizing their potential.

Another important factor is that language skills increase the self-confidence of young people. Students and pupils who know foreign languages can communicate freely, do not hesitate to share their opinions with their foreign peers, which ensures their psychological maturity and active participation in society. By learning a language, young people learn to look at problems from different perspectives, which forms them as people who think in a holistic way and are open to innovation.

Language skills also play an important role in the creative activities of young people. Many young people from Uzbekistan write poems, articles, stories in foreign languages, and create their own content on platforms such as YouTube. This educates them not only as consumers, but also as creative, innovative thinkers. In this regard, language skills give an absolute advantage for creative fields such as translation, literature, cinema, journalism, advertising, and design.

From an economic point of view, young people who know languages will have the opportunity to work remotely for foreign investors, international companies and companies located abroad. This will increase their income, gain experience and benefit the country. In particular, the development of the "freelance" sector is opening up wide opportunities for young people who know languages.

At the same time, knowing languages also serves national interests. Young people who know languages are important for protecting the interests of Uzbekistan in the international arena, expanding scientific and diplomatic relations, and working with foreign investors and tourists. Therefore, learning foreign languages is not only a personal necessity, but also a necessity for the development of the country.

In our country, there is increasing attention to an intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages. Through this, young people understand the cultures of other peoples in the process of learning foreign languages, and at the same time, they also understand their own national values. This process serves to form cultural integration, tolerance and global citizenship.

Another important aspect is that the process of learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan is carried out in harmony with the national mentality and respect for the native language. Knowledge of a foreign language is not considered a way to forget the native language, but rather a necessity for the development of bilingualism and multilingualism. Through this, young people not only find themselves in the global arena, but also can promote their national values abroad. Knowledge of foreign languages also has a great impact on the personal and cultural development of young people. Through language, getting acquainted with the history, culture, traditions of other nations forms mutual respect and tolerance. At the same time, learning a language also develops critical thinking, analytical analysis, and a creative approach. These are important competencies for active participation in modern society. Future professions, especially in such areas as IT, tourism, diplomacy, international law, journalism, medicine, and marketing, consider knowledge of a foreign language necessary. Therefore, the desire of today's youth to learn languages ensures their competitiveness in a market economy. In Uzbekistan, knowledge of foreign languages is being formed not only as a means of working abroad, but also as a criterion for becoming a highly qualified, modern-

thinking specialist in one's own country.

It should be noted that some problems are also encountered in the process of learning a language. For example, the lack of quality textbooks, qualified teachers, and practice-oriented methodologies remains a problem in some places. However, systematic work is being carried out to eliminate these.

Conclusion

The interest in learning foreign languages among the youth of Uzbekistan serves to ensure the country's active participation in the global arena, the intellectual potential and competitiveness of young people. Language learning today has become not only a means of communication, but also the key to personal and professional development. Supporting this process and developing it based on modern methods has a positive impact not only on the education system, but also on the overall development of society. In the future, language-savvy, open-minded, and qualified young people will undoubtedly become the country's most important intellectual resource.

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